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BioExcel-2 Project Number 823830

D6.2 – Quality Assurance and Risk Management Plan

WP6: Management

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Executive Summary

This document builds on D6.1 – Management plan (where we presented the operational structure of the project) and discusses the overall quality monitoring process for the project. Particular attention is given to the review process of deliverables and annual reports as well as milestone completion. Success criteria and KPIs are described and their status will be followed-up in the management reports. An additional section covers the overall contingency strategy where potential risks are identified for monitoring and regular assessment in the periodic management reports.

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1 Introduction

The objective of the quality assurance and risk management plan is to define the processes, plans and metrics that shall apply throughout the BioExcel project in order to monitor the activities, to identify and eliminate potential risks, and to ensure the successful execution of the project. Deliverable review procedures and reporting timelines are also defined to guarantee the quality aspired for. The guidelines apply to all work packages.

In addition to the list of KPIs covering the whole project, we are providing in appendix an extended list of GROMACS-related metrics, sub-KPIs. These metrics describe expected trends in the GROMACS software capabilities, and the development process around it. Initially, the focus suits the needs of GROMACS development work within BioExcel. If successful, the GROMACS team may generalize the sub-KPIs for their needs and promote their adoption by third-party software developers.

2 Quality Assurance Action Plan

The quality assurance action plan addresses establishment of 1) an operational structure, 2) processes for monitoring of activities and their results, 3) mitigation strategies of potential risks.

In D6.1 we have described in detail the project organization and management structure (Figure 1). Here we first give a brief overview followed by elaboration on the operational processes and assessment of results along main lines of center activities.

Figure 1. Organization chart of the centre

2.1 Operational structure and general processes

The main driving body of the center activities is the Executive Board (EB) team. It is composed of all WP leaders, their deputies, the Executive, Scientific and Commercial Directors. In order to ensure appropriate involvement and communication channels, partners, who are not represented in the EB either as WP leaders or deputies, are also invited to the EB meetings.

EB videoconference meetings are organized twice per month. During the meetings, each WP leader (or deputy in the event of absence) presents the status of ongoing activities and the plans for future ones. The Executive Director and EB members ensure that those activities are in line with, and work towards the objectives described in the DoA. Each of the WP leaders is responsible for monitoring and meeting the metrics (Table 2. Key Performance Indicators), the milestones, preparing the deliverables and managing potential risks (Table 3)

All partners submit project internal quarterly reports to the Executive Director. The reports include:

- 1) description of accomplishments along the tasks assigned to the partner,
- 2) issues that are being observed
- 3) recommendation for improvement of the operations and
- 4) consumed effort during the reporting period.

Issues, which cannot be resolved at the operational EB level such as insufficient staff, consistent underperformance of personnel, global dangers for success of the project etc. are brought up to the corresponding PI, member of the Project Management Board (PMB), or the whole PMB, where applicable.

The Executive Director and the project office analyze the consumed effort and in the case of discrepancy the issue is discussed directly with the corresponding partner.

In the following sections we elaborate on some of the main procedures that have been established to ensure success of the project.

2.2 Deliverable review process

Every deliverable has a designated person responsible for its preparation, and that is typically the leader of the corresponding WP. The rest of the partners with effort in the given WP provide input to the leader for preparation of the document. The draft document is reviewed by at least three different partners who have little or no effort in the given WP while having related competency (Table 1).

WP #	Lead beneficiary	Main contributors	Reviewing partners
WP1	KTH	UU, JYU, MPG, UEDIN, JUELICH	IRB, UMAN, BSC
WP2	IRB	UNIMAN, EBI, BSC, KTH	KTH, UU, MPG
WP3	UEDIN	KTH, UU, IRB, UNIMAN, JYU	IHC, EBI, NBD
WP4	EBI	KTH, AL	UEDIN, JUELICH, JYU, NC
WP5	AL	KTH, IHC, NC, NBD	UEDIN, BSC, NBD
WP6	KTH		IHC, NC, AL

Table 1. Leaders and reviewers of deliverables.

The review process is as follows:

1. Deliverable leaders collect material from partners and provide the first draft for review **4 weeks** before submission deadline
2. Iterative **reviewing** process continues for the **following two weeks**
3. Second draft is submitted to the Project Management Board (PMB) **two weeks** before submission deadline
4. Comments are addressed and final version is ready **1 week** before submission deadline. The last week is used for final formatting changes and document is submitted to EC.

Important issues with deliverable preparation and submission are discussed within EB or raised to PMB, if needed.

2.3 Periodic reports and Milestones

In addition to the main deliverables, the project produces the following outcomes:

- Quarterly reports - internal
- Annual reports – to be submitted to EC
- Financial reports – internal, twice per year
- Financial annual reports – to be submitted to EC
- Milestones

Quarterly reports are produced by each partner and serve as base for deliverables as well as annual reports.

Annual reports are prepared according to the same process used for the deliverables described above.

Financial reports are prepared by the Project Office. The bi-annual reports are used for internal monitoring of effort expenditure, while the annual ones (or as requested) are submitted to EC.

Milestones have clearly identified due dates in the DoA and responsible partners. When a milestone has been reached, the partner responsible needs to inform the EB and provide sufficient documentation which proves that the milestone has been reached. This documentation will subsequently be included in the next periodic report.

2.4 Software development

The consortium supports developers of several software applications as well as experts of the supported workflow systems. Quality assurance process for the developed code and adoption of best practices are explained in detail in deliverable “D1.1. Updated specification of development process”.

2.5 Training

Quality assurance in the training activities requires success in:

- Understanding the needs of the community

- Clearly defined audience for training resources (e.g. tutorials, events)
- Development of relevant training material to address those needs
- Establishment of wide dissemination channels with the community
- Delivery of a quality training programme
- Long-term impact assessment of the training programme

To understand the needs, we have already connected with and surveyed the large user base of the three main codes and workflow systems. The currently available training material is assessed (<http://krc.bioexcel.eu/>) and plans have been made for new development. The mapping of the training resources to the BioExcel competency profile will be described in D4.2 and included in the Knowledge Resource Center (KRC).

To assess the quality of the training programme we capture post-course feedback in a standardized survey. To analyse the impact of the programme we send out surveys to participants after 6-12 months and well as 2 years after the course.

WP4 organizes regular telecons for organization and monitoring of the progress in the training and dissemination (section 2.6) activities.

2.6 Dissemination and outreach

Adequate dissemination of the results and outreach to the communities is of vital importance. The process for ensuring success includes:

- Social media strategy
 - Further exploitation of the established channels (Twitter and LinkedIn).
 - A dedicated person is responsible for monitoring of the website content and the status of the social media channel engagement and development
- Web content
 - Web content creation is divided in several topical categories, in general corresponding to the different activities in centre. Content will be created regularly in the respective categories as the project evolves and results are produced.
 - Web content addition is overseen by the web curator who is also responsible for monitoring of the social media channel activities.
- Promotion material
 - Current promotion material (such as flyers, poster, roll-up) will be updated and distributed to partners. Once per year we are planning to revise the content and update according to the progress in the project activities.

3 Timeline of activities

The Gantt chart on p.11-12 shows the timing of the work packages and their deliverables and milestones

4 Success metrics and KPIs

Achievement of scientific excellence and impact are at the core of BioExcel and as such they underlie the performance indicators that will be used to monitor the success of project. Three pillars form the basis of our approach for achieving this excellence and impact (Figure 2).

Figure 2. BioExcel Pillars of Excellence

In the following sections we will give a brief overview of the metrics for success in each of the pillars, while in section 4.5 we provide a more detailed description of the associated KPIs.

4.1 Software Excellence

Our software activities aim to improve the availability, efficiency, scalability and usability of the selected Life Science software packages of high importance and usage for the field. These form the BioExcel core applications, and are GROMACS, HADDOCK, pmx, and QM/MM using CP2K.

Maintenance and possibly increase of scaling and efficiency on modern hardware as demonstrated by regular benchmarking, measured as absolute performance and relative scaling. This will depend heavily on the characteristics of next generation hardware. A baseline of 5% annual software performance improvement is expected from a subset of our core applications, but actual improvement could be considerably higher. This will be reported on as part of the set of KPIs adopted for GROMACS development.

Porting and improving performance/scaling of codes to new emerging architectures including accelerators. Depending on the availability and usefulness of new platforms we aim for two such architectures.

Increasing the quality of scientific software through professional Quality Assurance (specific targets for the development process for each application will be chosen as part of D1.1 at PM4). Quality will for instance be quantified by reporting on number and severity of bugs found and fixed through targeting testing on workflows found to be important to the members of the user groups, or reporting the annual increase in the fractions of the code bases covered by unit and regression tests.

4.2 Usability Excellence

A main objective of our activity along this pillar is to increase the usability of e-Infrastructures by enabling easy access to computing and data resources through workflow environments and associated data management tools and portals. Excellence in usability is ultimately linked to excellence in the software use and adoption. Those will be quantified through user-group reports of benefits derived from learning how to use the software better on current and new platforms and infrastructures.

4.3 Support and training excellence

Our support activities will enhance the uptake of computational technologies both in academic and industrial user groups and provide feedback and requirements to other activities such as user-driven software development and business model development. The training and dissemination function will ensure that all stakeholders properly benefit from the CoE. This means targeting and interacting with academic and industrial end-users, software developers, hardware and e-Infrastructure providers by developing workshops and training sessions for end users. Successful implementation of new technologies, and new approaches using existing technologies, will be presented in the context of the Use Cases as relevant demonstrator projects that push the envelope. Best Practice guides in response to user/community needs will be produced, and effort will be taken towards advancement of standards.

4.4 Outreach and dissemination excellence

Online platforms and communication channels offer unprecedented opportunities for outreach to ever wider audiences. At the same time, the flood of information makes it very challenging to “break through the noise” to get users’ attention. To address this challenge, we will be developing and applying high standards in dissemination processes by preparing high quality promotional and marketing material, designing activities based on user feedback etc. The existence of alternative tools for molecular dynamic modelling and docking available from academic and commercial organisations requires that the dissemination process articulates how BioExcel offerings have distinctive capability and performance in terms of speed, scale, predictive power and applicability through workflows and portals.

4.5 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

To assess the impact of the project, Key Performance Indicators have been defined and will be monitored and reported in the management reports. Table 2 provides an extensive list of the metrics, their likelihood, impact etc.

The wider field of software development is struggling to define useful KPIs. As in other fields, once KPIs are defined and known to those whose performance is being measured there is significant risk of the KPI becoming useless as a metric. Many things that can be measured, e.g. rates of software paper citation, have no clear connection with daily decision making, and often have long times between decision and impact. It makes no sense to have a target of increasing citation rate by 10% per year, because the causes of such changes are often not under control of the authors. Yet if the citation rate had consistently increased and begins to drop, then the related team should be able to observe this and consider action. Evolving such metrics is ongoing research by IDEAS-ECP (<https://ideas-productivity.org/ideas-ecp/>) which is funded by the US-based Exascale Compute Project, and BioExcel has already made some input into their work. Based on preliminary work of IDEAS, the GROMACS team within BioExcel has constructed a large set of sub-KPIs that we will report during BioExcel-2. That process has already taught us that maintenance, support, optimization/scaling and code modernization are tasks that more readily lend themselves to visibility through KPIs than activities that extend feature capabilities of software. The latter are best reported through periodic statements about the capabilities, as the underlying nature is Boolean. In Bioexcel-2, the GROMACS team plans numerous of both kinds of activities, and we expect to learn that some of these KPIs are useful, and some are not. Accordingly, the GROMACS team has attached our current planned sub-KPIs as an Appendix to this deliverable report and expect to evolve it over time. The kinds of activities necessary for GROMACS are not applicable to the other software development efforts within WP1, so we regard this initiative of the GROMACS team as an experiment rather than an example that others might follow at this time. We will report summary statistics from them as part of the formal BioExcel KPI reporting process.

Table 2. Key Performance Indicators

ID	KPI	Justification	Additional details (if needed)	Reachable target	Stretch target
	Software development HADDOCK -				
WP1_KPI01	Usability of the HADDOCK webserver as measured by the number of active users - expressed as a % increase/decrease with respect to previous period	Impact in usability as demonstrated by the number of users - an active user is a user submitting at least one run to the web portal		10% increase over previous period	25% increase over previous period
WP1_KPI02	Number of HADDOCK server issues (bugs) solved as documented in the HADDOCK GitHub repository	Documented issues (classified as bug in GitHub) with the code should lead to actions/corrections.	These are mainly bug fixes to the existing server code. For usage stability we don't expect a large amount of changes	2/year	5/year
WP1_KPI03	Number of HADDOCK server issues (enhancements) implemented as documented in the HADDOCK GitHub repository	Documented feature requests (classified as enhancements in GitHub) should lead to new implementations in the code.	These are enhancement requests that will results in new features / possibilities of the webserver	2/year	5/year
WP1_KPI04	Number of HADDOCK software issues (bugs) solved as documented in the HADDOCK GitHub repository	Documented issues (classified as bug in GitHub) with the code should lead to actions/corrections.	These are mainly bug fixes to the existing code	10/year	20/year

WP1_KPI05	Number of HADDOCK software issues (enhancements) implemented as documented in the HADDOCK GitHub repository	Documented feature requests (classified as enhancements in GitHub) should lead to new implementations in the code.	These are enhancement requests that will result in new features / possibilities of the code	2/year	5/year
WP1_KPI06	Number of modules generated for HADDOCK	A major activity in WP1 is a complete rewrite in a modular fashion of HADDOCK. This will result in a completely new version of HADDOCK, with its own repository in GitHub (i.e. not a new branch)	This will result in a completely new version of HADDOCK, with its own repository in GitHub (i.e. not a new branch)	15 over the entire project	30 over the entire project
	Software development GROMACS -				
WP1_KPI07	Co-design projects	Successful co-design projects are the only viable path to exascale performance goals	Reported as one of the GROMACS sub-KPIs	3 co-design projects active or completed	5 co-design projects active or completed
WP1_KPI08	Performance and Scalability	Impact in exascale usage will be strongest when time to solution on concrete relevant use cases is minimized.	Reported in several of the GROMACS sub-KPIs	Relevant KPIs do not violate the expected trend or value	100% of relevant KPIs are reported to have the expected trend or value
WP1_KPI09	Software development process	Users are best served by a development team that understands how to show that it is working to update the legacy codebase to meet the requirements of the exascale era	Reported in several of the GROMACS sub-KPIs	Relevant KPIs do not violate the expected trend or value	100% of relevant KPIs are reported to have the expected trend or value
WP1_KPI10	Software capability	Users need new and improved functionality for exascale biomolecular simulations, and	Reported in several of the GROMACS sub-KPIs	80% of relevant KPIs are reported to have the expected trend	100% of relevant KPIs are reported to have the expected trend

		old functionality needs to be removed in due course			
WP1_KPI11	KPI automation	Reporting and acting on the many GROMACS KPIs is only sustainable if collection and presentation is automated	Reported as one of the GROMACS sub-KPIs	Reporting of 80% of KPIs is automated	Reporting of 100% of KPIs is automated
	Software development - CP2K				
WP1_KPI12	Performance & scalability	Specific performance & scalability improvements difficult to estimate at this stage. Approach will be iterations of benchmark, profile, analyse, implement.		5 strategies investigated for scalability improvement and documented	10 strategies investigated for scalability improvement and documented
WP1_KPI13	Availability	Since lead developers of CP2K are not in the project, and important measure of success is the extent to which code modifications are accepted into the core codebase, so that changes reach the wider community.	Contributions should be non-trivial and should benefit biomolecular researchers/use-cases. If BioExcel decides not to invest in code changes to CP2K, then no progress will be made on this KPI.	2 accepted contributions to main codebase	4 accepted contributions to codebase
WP1_KPI14	Novel hardware	Our work should benefit future systems, and not just be focused on immediate user needs		CP2K benchmarked on 1 novel platform	CP2K benchmarked on 2 novel platforms
WP1_KPI15	Software engineering	BioExcel CP2K development should positively influence code development process as well as code content.		1 new practice adopted by CP2K developers	2 new practices adopted by main CP2K development team
	Software development - PMX				

WP1_KPI16	Transition to Python 3	With the end of support for the Python 2 packages, a major re-write of PMX in Python 3 is required		33% of code ported to Python 3 every year	50% of code ported to Python 3 every year
WP1_KPI17	Feature development	New features to be added to the PMX infrastructure to fully automate free energy calculation setup		1 major feature a year	2 major features a year
	Convergence of HPC/HPDA and Improved Usability				
WP2_KPI01	Number of tools packaged in virtualized environments available from bio-repositories (bio.tools, biocontainers, bioconda) with BioExcel tag	The number of tools identified and registered by BioExcel defines and publicizes the power of the centre of excellence software infrastructure. ELIXIR bio.tools registry assures to reach a wider audience within the bioinformatics community. BioContainers (container-based technology) and BioConda (environment management) both provide system-agnostic executable environments for bioinformatics software	30 registered in bio.tools	50 (starting from 30 in BioExcel-1)	100
WP2_KPI02	Number of pre-Exascale-showcase workflows	Workflows developed in BioExcel-2 need to run properly in Exascale infrastructures. For that, different types of Exascale-prepared workflow managers will be used and the pipelines need to be tested in different		5 success stories, internal work published/presented in conferences	10 success stories, internal work published/presented in conferences

		HPC centres, from which benchmarking studies will be extracted. All the expertise acquired with these processes will be crucial for the CoE.			
WP2_KPI03	Number of workflows with HPC-HPDA technologies within	Workflows combining simulations, analytics & visualization, with the possibility to work with I/O streaming, and even with embedded HPDA methods making them change the conditions while being executed (dynamic workflows) will be the state-of-the-art technology for the Exascale era. BioExcel as a CoE needs to lead the way.		5 success stories, internal work published/presented in conferences	10 success stories, internal work published/presented in conferences
WP2_KPI04	Number of external (non-BioExcel) researchers using the developed workflows.	Success in leading the Biomolecular simulations research can be undeniably measured by external usage of our developed workflows.		6 scientific publications/drafts/external success stories using BioExcel-developed workflows	10 scientific publications/drafts/external success stories using BioExcel-developed workflows
WP2_KPI05	Number of workflows installed in virtualized environments (VMs, Containers) available from the BioExcel Cloud Portal	The number of workflows developed by BioExcel and available for the community through the Cloud Portal is key for the usability & visibility (easy access), reproducibility (containerized environments)	Starting from MCDNA, Chromatin Dynamics, MDSetup, PyMDSetup (mutations), NAFlex, CPMD public, CPMD private	20 (starting from 7** in BioExcel-1)	40

		and training (easy deployment in workshop events).			
WP2_KPI06	Number of events run using the BioExcel Cloud Portal	The BioExcel Cloud Portal automatic VMs/Containers deployment was tested in a training event in BioExcel. The number of events run in BioExcel-2 using the Cloud Portal functionalities will measure its maturity.		3 (1/Year)	6 (2/year)
	User Driven Development				
WP3_KPI01	Number of community members from whom input has been gathered	Ensure that users' needs are conveyed to the project/centre. This figure includes all types of feedback/input.		150/year	300/year
WP3_KPI02	Number of community members supported	Provide additional support (to code users, and biomolecular researchers in general) through multiple channels, in varying levels of depth. Figure represents all types of support.	720 by end of project	900 by end of project	30
WP3_KPI03	Number of online tutorials	New tutorials describing new features and specific usage scenarios of the code		5/year	10/year
WP3_KPI04	Number of questions answered on the ask.bioexcel.eu forum, compared to the previous period	User support for the various software. This depends of course on the user input/questions		10% increase per year	25% increase per year

	Training				
WP4_KPI01	Number of CoE training events, including webinars, face-to-face training courses and virtual training sessions	Training covering the main areas of expertise in the centre should be provided at a reasonable frequency	Reported per quarterly report	3 events per quarterly report	5 events per quarterly report
WP4_KPI02	Post-course feedback; applies to F2F and virtual training courses (excluding pilot)	Rating of the training course based on the participant course feedback survey	Feedback data collected in surveymonkey; average across quarterly report	75% responses "Good" or "Excellent"	90% responses "Good" or "Excellent"
WP4_KPI03	Post-course feedback - response percentage; applies to F2F and virtual training courses (excluding pilot)	Measure of how representative the collected feedback is	Correlate attendance number with Surveymonkey responses; average across quarterly report	70% response rate for feedback survey	90% response rate for feedback survey
WP4_KPI04	Post-course feedback - response percentage; applies to F2F and virtual training courses (excluding pilot)	Measure of how representative the collected feedback is	Correlate email invite with Surveymonkey responses - average across quarterly report	15% response rate for long-term feedback survey	20% response rate for long-term feedback survey
WP4_KPI05	Faculty Gender balance (organisers, speakers, facilitators, TAs)	Gender balance is a known issue in this field, we want to measure how we are doing and improve so that we can set a good example	Taken from course page, all individuals taken into the count should be clearly listed on the course page	25%	35%
WP4_KPI06	Number of entries in the Knowledge Resource Centre	Measure of the curation of content in the KRC	Number of resources added, removed or otherwise curated during quarterly report. The content in the KRC needs to be kept up to date to provide maximum value for the user	30	45

	Dissemination and outreach				
WP4_KPI07	Social media - Twitter	Regular engagement and updates are needed for social media channels	Total tweets per quarterly report - collected from twitter analytics. <25 slow month; 25-40 standard month; 40-50 Excellent month. Reachable = 3x lower standard range, Stretch = 3x lower excellent range	75 tweets per quarter	120 tweets per quarter
WP4_KPI08	Number of new Twitter followers	Determine whether our reach on twitter is increasing	Total followers per quarterly report - collected from twitter analytics. <30 slow month; 30-50 standard month; 50-80 Excellent month. Reachable = 3x lower standard range, Stretch = 3x lower excellent range	90 new followers per quarter	150 new followers per quarter
WP4_KPI09	Social media - LinkedIn	Regular engagement and updates are needed for social media channels	Total per quarterly report - collected from LinkedIn Analytics. <8 slow month; 08-15 standard month; 15-20 Excellent month. Reachable = 3x lower standard range, Stretch = 3x lower excellent range	24 update per quarter	45 update per quarter
WP4_KPI10	Number of website visits	This KPI helps to determine whether we are increasing our reach as well as when peak interaction periods are	Total per quarterly report - collected from google analytics. <1100 slow month; 1100 - 1500 standard month; 1500< Excellent month. Reachable = 3x lower standard range, Stretch = 3x lower excellent range	3300 per month	4500 per quarter

WP4_KPI11	Number of people subscribed to the general BioExcel mailing list (potentially to be renamed to "Join BioExcel")	Determine whether our reach is increasing	Login to website < MailPoet < Subscribers < BioExcel mailinglist (XXX). Report increase from last quarter <10 slow month, 10-15 standard month, 15< excellent month. Reachable = 3x lower standard range, Stretch = 3x lower excellent range	30	45
Sustainable Business Model					
WP5_KPI01	Number of BioExcel branded services (training courses / workflow / quality mark / others) ready for commercial use	Service provisioning will be fundamental for the success of the centre		1 per year	2 per year
WP5_KPI02	Number of entities in pipeline showing interest in BioExcel commercial services	Need to ensure meaningful engagement with potential customers for the centre offerings. The entities will include pharma, agrifood, SMEs, ISVs, HPC centres, non-profit organizations and academia	Evidence of engagement needs to be provided. Different stages of engagement to be defined and we need to show that an entity is moving through them	3 per year	6 per year
WP5_KPI03	Number of commercial offers sent to entities	Need to start business-like operations with clear pitching to potential industrial clients		5 per year	8 per year

5 Risk Management

Establishing a Centre of Excellence (CoE) is a complex task that carries risks not only associated with the execution of the project but also ones that are related to achieving the ultimate goal of a sustainable organization. The consortium has the experiences and required know-how in biomolecular Life Science, parallel applications, HPC (exascale) and HTC technologies, and providing support for academic and industrial user groups in the field, for a successful execution of the project work-plan and the setup of a sustainable CoE.

The implementation of risk management processes are crucial in order to mitigate undesired outcomes. In Table 3 we present a list of identified potential risks, both for the execution of the project and the longer-term success of the CoE. We have put in place the following methodology for monitoring, analysis and action plan regarding those risks:

- WP leaders are responsible for continuously monitoring the progress along the objectives in their work packages. The monitoring relies on sufficient communication with the corresponding WP members. Identified issues are brought up at the next executive board (EB) meeting. If there's been a consistent problem with intra-work package communication, the case is escalated to the responsible partner PIs, which are members of the project management board (PMB).
- During EB meetings the issues are brought up and their scope, severity of impact, priority for resolving and suggested action plan are discussed. If the risk concerns a single WP, its leader will be in charge to execute actions, as agreed by the board. If the scope covers more than a single work package, leaders of all affected work packages are required to implement coordinated efforts and the necessary actions for resolving them.
- In case of conflicts, the issues are raised to the PMB and dealt with according to the conflict resolution strategy based on the Consortium Agreement, as outlined in D6.1 "Management plan".
- Risks with high rating (= Likelihood x Impact, see Table 3), are noted as "high risk factors" and are given special attention for monitoring and implementation of preventive or counteractive measures.
- Risks will be evaluated quarterly.

The risk management plan thus ensures that risks are identified, brought to the attention of concerned personnel and counter measures are put in place. Close interactions between WP leaders and their deputies within the EB, as well as at the higher management level of PMB, will guarantee that mitigation strategies are executed in due time. Monitoring and planning are supported by the roadmap (based on the description of work) of milestones and deliverables, as well as the internal periodic reporting. We have also setup a database for tracking issues that have arisen, the actions taken and their outcome.

WP1 in BioExcel has identified several particular risks associated with our plans to improve QM/MM support with CP2K. Unlike the other core codes of BioExcel, where the main development teams form an integral part of BioExcel, the main CP2K

development team is outside BioExcel. This bears the risks that BioExcel won't find developers with the necessary CP2K skills and that it is impractical for us to make significant improvements to QM/MM in CP2K. It is also possible that those we make would not be welcomed as contributions by the main CP2K development team. We are taking appropriate actions to avoid and mitigate such risks, including the CP2K benchmarking report in Deliverable 1.1 at PM4.

Table 3. Risks and mitigation actions. WP is the affected workpackage. Its leader is responsible for monitoring the corresponding risk.

Abbreviations: L (Likelihood); I (Impact); R (Rating=Likelihood x Impact); Ops (Operational); Comm (Communications); Ext (External). Color coding of rating: Green=low, Yellow=medium, Red=High

Risk #	Description	WP	Likelihood	Impact	Risk score	Proposed Mitigation actions
Risks for the project execution					(Likelihood x Impact)	
R1	Changes to future hardware roadmaps	WP1	1	5	5	If processor architectures change significantly, BioExcel will focus on the most important products in the market, or those for which the broadest end-user impact is expected. In this case we will alter priorities between accelerators, heterogeneous parallelization and scaling to focus on the largest impact for end users.
R2	Applications cannot efficiently exploit/scale on new hardware	WP1	1	5	5	The current code versions efficiently exploit and are scalable on a wide range of architectures. Through our co- design activities we ensure that future hardware developments take our requirements into account.
R3	Dependencies of core applications (e.g. Fortran, C++, Python, CUDA, OpenCL, FFTW) unusable on extreme scale platforms	WP1	2	4	8	Depending on external libraries is a standard software engineering technique to accelerate the development process. Those for BioExcel core applications are already chosen with due care (but see Risk 4). If such dependencies are not available on extreme scale platforms, then alternatives will be explored and/or deployed.
R4	Computational engine of HADDOCK (CNS - third party software) no longer developed / supported on new architectures	WP1	2	4	8	CNS is still under development and existing WP1 plans for modularisation of HADDOCK will allow to replace some (but not all) components. This will also depend on the specific docking scenario. If CNS becomes unsuitable for use, then we will re-prioritize effort here.

R5	Software alternatives to BioExcel core applications become dominant user choices	WP1	2	5	10	If user activity through WP3 identifies rapid growth in popularity of software offering similar functionality to the BioExcel core applications, we will reconsider development plans. This might include implementing comparable features, porting to new platforms, or in highly unlikely extreme cases ceasing development.
R6	Planned optimizations in CP2K may not lead to better performing or scaling code.	WP1	3	4	12	Optimization is not always successful. Our iterative approach will allow for consideration of multiple possible optimizations. Results will be analyzed, and unsuccessful optimizations will be analyzed and documented to produce concrete output to inform future possible optimization efforts.
R7	CP2K work undertaken by BioExcel may not be adopted into the main code distribution	WP1	2	4	8	Establish and maintain connections with CP2K lead developers early. Ensure that BioExcel conforms to their expectations.
R8	CP2K codebase is a moving target leading to BioExcel work becoming out of date	WP1	3	2	6	Monitor new versions of code under development to identify any with an overlap with BioExcel's work. Negotiate according to the situation.
R9	Discovery of missing requirements or finding of unsolvable steps during development.	WP1/2	4	3	12	The development of the core applications will be guided by concrete use cases and user requirements. The modular nature of the computational framework used will ease adaptation to new requirements.
R10	Workflow systems prove difficult to exploit HPC platforms	WP2	3	3	9	Partners have extensive experience in a range of workflow and distributed system platforms, and a mixed portfolio of systems will mitigate the risk.
R11	Services offered by CoE are not attractive to the wider user community	WP3	3	4	12	Ensure that service roll-outs include monitoring of user uptake. Ensure service offering is clearly communicated to potential users. Change service offering if necessary.

R12	Potential users locked-in to existing communities and support structures	WP3	3	2	6	Ensure that our offering promotes features that others don't have. Look for means to integrate with existing support infrastructure. Finally, if the external offering remains more compelling, consider withdrawing from active support in areas where it is difficult to compete and promote existing support mechanisms.
R13	Failing to deliver project results and training to relevant audience	WP4	2	4	8	Training activities will be closely aligned with those of related initiatives such as CECAM, PRACE PATCs, EOSC- Hub, EMBL-EBI, ELIXIR/Instruct etc. We have already established a number of MoUs with some of these organizations. Further, the quarterly internal reports will allow tight monitoring of the progress and allow to take early action when required.
R14	Low numbers of delegates at training events or workshops	WP4	2	5	10	Effective promotion of events beginning several months before the event. Ideally registration should be open 6 months in advance with promotion of the event starting earlier or at the same time. Developing training that is specifically aimed towards filling perceived (and real) gaps in training. Travel grants to mitigate financial burden of attending training events.
R15	Impossible to reach an agreement among founders regarding the structure and operations of the BioExcel independent legal entity	WP5	3	4	12	Consider alternative structure and setup that is accepted by a sufficient number of core founders
R16	Business exploitable assets do not adequately address industry needs	WP5	3	5	15	Keep constant discussions with industry and close feedback loop with WP1-4 personnel
R17	Business exploitable assets are launched too early to market, provided at more attractive prices or better quality by other organizations	WP5	3	5	15	Carefully consider whether business plans and service catalog offerings (e.g. as those included in deliverables and reports) should be shared with the wider public.
R18	Non-availability of the BioExcel website, support forum or portals of the associated software applications and tools	WP6	3	5	15	The website is hosted in Sweden with automated backups taken daily. Additional server is available in Spain and can be used as a backup in case of

						emergency. All web-infrastructure (website, forums, social channels etc.) has multiple people with administrative privileges for support.
R19	Partner is not competent to carry out allocated tasks.	WP6	1	5	5	Partners have been carefully selected based on different required expertise (high performance and high throughput computing, biomolecular life science, software development, scientific & industrial applications), track record in their field (number of scientific publications and citations for research partners; level of innovation; academic excellence) and balance of the consortium. The consortium agreement includes measures to be taken if a partner still would not deliver for some reason, such as replacement of this partner by another one and a corresponding budget reallocation.
R20	Key staff leave or are unexpectedly absent (WP leaders, EB members etc)	WP6	3	4	12	Regular communication, deputies if applicable and in case of resignation a hand-over period will be used to facilitate a smooth transition. Staff might be more likely to leave towards the end of funding (e.g. for new projects) - to mitigate more than 1 staff at each partner should be kept in the loop (e.g. lurk on mailing lists, local update meetings).

6 BioExcel Quality Mark

BioExcel strives for excellence in all aspects of its activities – operations, products, services, community support, stakeholder engagement etc. One of our main goals is the development of a quality mark against which we will measure our progress. The quality assurance processes, performance metrics and risks management outlined above will play a main role in the development of the quality mark. The full description of the latter will be provided in “D5.1 Branding and Quality Mark Design Inception Report [PM6]”. A related goal is to establish the quality mark as a certificate of excellence which can be later applied to other related initiatives and ultimately become part of the BioExcel product portfolio.

7 Appendix: GROMACS-oriented sub-KPIs

7.1 Introduction

These key performance indicators (KPIs) describe expected trends in the GROMACS software capabilities, and the development process around it. They are chosen to be

- Useful indicators of desirable progress toward capabilities desired by users,
- Quantifiable,
- Able to be measured with minimal ongoing human involvement,
- Able to be rationalized when violated appropriately, and
- Suggestive of remedial action when violated inappropriately.

Each KPI has a justification of why the trend is expected, a proposed technique for automated measurement, an interval at which it will be measured and recorded, and planned remedial actions. Initially the focus suits the needs of BioExcel, but if successful the GROMACS team may generalize the KPIs for their own needs. Other KPIs have been considered and rejected because they fail one of the above criteria, but we may list such “inactive but possibly desirable” KPIs in future.

In general, KPIs will refer to the state of GROMACS website, source code master branch, Redmine issue-tracking server, or Gerrit code-review server on a given date, which by default is the fifth of each month (to reduce clashes with other first-of-the-month recurring tasks). Where appropriate, existing or new clang-tidy checks will be deployed.

If the KPI is not satisfied in a reporting period, the default action will be to understand and report on why, and either plan remedial action, or (rarely) modify the KPI to be a better reflection of desirable performance. Other planned actions are noted as appropriate. It is expected that from time to time there will be noticeable jumps in some measurements, such as when adding or removing large pieces of code or external dependencies. These will be recorded, and where possible an estimate made of how to compare numbers measured before and after the unusual event.

Some of the infrastructure for KPI reporting will also be able to be repurposed, e.g. to report performance benchmarks alongside new releases.

This is a living document and will evolve after its initial application as part of the BioExcel-2 Deliverable 6.2. Any code or scripts will be contributed to the GROMACS master branch and updated periodically. Reporting on observations and planned actions will take place in the BioExcel-2 periodic report, the GROMACS Redmine issue tracker and on the GROMACS website.

7.2 Software Development Process

7.2.1 Modularity

Number of modules increases

- Justification: A modular code base is better able to adapt to changing requirements and team composition to deliver value to users
- Measurement: Count number of subdirectories of `src/gromacs` and `src/programs`

Changes in size of largest non-legacy module are considered for action

- Justification: Adding a new large module may make the code base harder to understand
- Measurement: Count the number of lines of code, number of files, number of structs+classes+enums+free functions in each module, and record the module with the largest value for each metric

Changes in size of smallest module are considered for action

- Justification: Having small modules may make the code base harder to understand
- Measurement: Count the number of lines of code, number of files, number of structs+classes+enums+free functions in each module, and record the module with the smallest value for each metric

Increases in number of module cyclic dependencies are considered for action

- Justification: Modules that depend circularly on each other are not modular, and make the code base harder to maintain than a levelized code base.
- Measurement: Count the number of non-comment lines in docs/doxygen/cycle-suppressions.txt

Number of legacy modules decreases

- Justification: Code in modules not deliberately constructed is prone to bugs, hard to understand, and hard to modify.
- Measurement: Reported by GROMACS check-source

Number of files in legacy modules decreases

- Justification: Code in modules not deliberately constructed is prone to bugs, hard to understand, and hard to modify.
- Measurement: Count the number of files in modules described as legacy by GROMACS check-source

7.2.2 Code quality

Number of raw memory allocation calls decreases

- Justification: Resources should be managed with RAII to decrease the defect rate observed by users, particularly for long-running, API-driven, or extreme-scale applications:
<http://isocpp.github.io/CppCoreGuidelines/CppCoreGuidelines#Rr-raii>
- Measurement: clang-tidy check

Number of raw memcpy decreases

- Justification: Management of buffer contents through operations using raw pointers and/or sizes carries greater risk of use-after-free and use-with-wrong-bounds problems than via encapsulated objects.
- Measurement: clang-tidy check

Number of raw file handles decreases

- Justification: As above
- Measurement: clang-tidy check

Number of raw GPU resource handles decreases

- Justification: As above
- Measurement: clang-tidy check

Number of TODO / fixme comments in the code does not increase dramatically

- Justification: Known issues in the code base should be addressed eventually at an appropriate time relative to the value delivered to end users from addressing them
- Measurement: Count using grep for strings like “TODO”, “\todo”, “to-do”, “FIX ME”, “fixme”, etc.

Number of clang-tidy checkers active increases

- Justification: The clang-tidy tool contains numerous code quality checkers contributed by other C++ development teams that if satisfied will lead to fewer code defects for users.
- Measurement: Count the checks enabled in src/.clang-tidy configuration file

Number of files with Doxygen comments increases

- Justification: Developers will be better able to maintain and extend documented code, delivering value to users.
- Measurement:

Number of C-style opaque structs decreases

- Justification: Hiding implementation details behind interfaces is desirable, but using multiple styles within the same code base confuses developers about expectations
- Measurement: Count using grep the total occurrences of “typedef struct”

Number of non-const pointer parameters decreases

- Justification: Non-const pointer parameters should often be replaced by return values, perhaps combined with struct, std::pair, gmx::compat::optional, or gmx::compat::expected because these are easier for developers to understand and use. In other cases, a view of memory into which to store output quantities is an appropriate replacement.
- Measurement: Count using clang tooling the total occurrences of non-const pointer parameters to functions, excluding those passed to external APIs.

Number of const pointer parameters decreases

- Justification: The accepted code style is to use const references for read-only function parameters
- Measurement: Count using clang tooling the total occurrences of const pointer parameters to functions, excluding those passed to external APIs.

Number of instances of code using deprecated interfaces decreases (e.g. parse_common_args, read_first_x/read_next_x, t_topology, t_param, t_param,

t_atomtype, t_molinfo, t_restp, t_hackblock, t_rbondeds, t_atomprop, gmx_residuetype_t)

- Justification: It is easier to work with code bases that have few, well-maintained, tested and documented ways to do things.
- Measurement: Count using `grep` the number of occurrences of each function or type identified as legacy

Number of modules that cannot write output to TNG files decreases

- Justification: Exascale simulations will not be able to be performant and write output to multiple different kinds of files, particularly text files. We need to extend the output functionality and deprecate the old functionality.
- Measurement: Count using `grep` or `clang` tooling the number of modules that use calls in the `tng_io` API (or other APIs that wrap them)

Number of modules that write to stdout or stderr decreases

- Justification: GROMACS output has historically tended to be verbose about things that users can't/won't/don't act upon. Such output might be usefully written in a verbose mode once more use is made of the logging feature. Decreasing calls to `stderr` and `stdout` is a proxy for uses of that logging feature.
- Measurement: Count using `grep` or `clang` tooling the number of calls to raw C APIs, particularly `printf`, `fprintf` and `fputs` using `stderr` and `stdout`

Number of `#define` preprocessor statements decreases

- Justification: Most uses of the C preprocessor can be replaced by superior constructions, including `constexpr` and templates. Using `#define` statements in headers like `config.h` (or equivalent) is expected, however.
- Measurement: Count using `grep` the number of `#define` statements

Number of `#ifdef` preprocessor statements decreases

- Justification: This construction is prone to silently permitting bugs
- Measurement: Count using `grep` the `#ifdef` statements

Number of non-annotated `#if` preprocessor statements decreases

- Justification: Sometimes a conventional `if` statement is sufficient. The main exceptions are when certain build configurations are using an external API that will not compile for other configurations; such legitimate uses should be annotated.
- Measurement: Count using `grep` the non-annotated `#if` statements

Distribution of cyclomatic complexity for each function in the code base tends towards (more of) smaller and simpler functions

- Justification: Complex functionality built from simple components is better able to be tested, understood, and extended. Accordingly, we expect to see a trend towards more and simpler functions, and will wish to act to correct any contrary trend. This could also be valuable to study for individual code modules.

- Measurement: Use a tool like Lizard (<http://www.lizard.ws/#>) to measure the cyclomatic complexity of each function and report summary statistics for the distribution for the whole code base, or perhaps each module.

7.2.3 Project management

All open Redmine issues marked “Feature” have targets

- Justification: Users and developers often propose features that are useful but which are not current priorities. Those should be triaged, and either rejected, targeted on the current upcoming release, or targeted on a placeholder release.
- Measurement: Query the Redmine API

All open Redmine issues marked “Task” have targets

- Justification: As above
- Measurement: Query the Redmine API

All Redmine issues marked “Bug” have an initial response and triage

- Justification: People who report bugs appreciate an acknowledgement, and are more likely to provide useful supporting information while the incident is fresh in their memory. Developer priorities need to be adjusted to meet upcoming release expectations according to the impact of the bug, if accepted.
- Measurement: Query the Redmine API

All open Redmine issues marked “Bug” have an assignee

- Justification: A bug that has not been rejected needs an assignee who will at least coordinate the response process
- Measurement: Query the Redmine API

Average duration between Redmine issues marked “Bug” being accepted and resolved is stable or decreasing compared with long-term baseline

- Justification: Sufficient time needs to be allocated to maintenance to support user needs, for which this is a proxy
- Measurement: Query the Redmine API

Number of Redmine issues with no response does not increase

- Justification: A human being thought this was important, and healthy developer community can at least agree with them but note that it is not a priority for current resources, or similar.
- Measurement: Query the Redmine API

Number of unique git contributors per month is stable or increasing compared with long-term baseline

- Justification: Users are best served by a healthy developer community
- Measurement: Query the git source repository over all active branches

Number of unique Gerrit patch sets opened in the last month

- Justification: Users are best served by a healthy developer community proposing changes to the code. This metric could be gamed easily, but such behaviour by individuals will be easy to see and correct.
- Measurement: Query the gerrit API, separately per active branch

Number of unique Gerrit patch sets closed in the last month

- Justification: Users are best served by a healthy developer community agreeing on proposed changes to the code, whether merging or abandoning the proposals. This also incentivizes closing proposals that have not generated interest, or that are now out of date.
- Measurement: Query the gerrit API, separately per active branch

Quarterly project plans covering development team at KTH are made

- Justification: Core developers at KTH need to understand what are the expectations on them so that we can deliver value to users on time and harmoniously
- Measurement: Quarterly sub-projects exist, issues are assigned to them and a draft time plan exists

Quarterly project plans covering development team at KTH are updated as the quarter progresses

- Justification: As above
- Measurement: As above

7.2.4 Review process

Average duration of Gerrit change requests authored by BioExcel developers is stable or decreasing compared with long-term baseline

- Justification: BioExcel developers have expectations on their process expressed in deliverable 1.1, both in terms of writing commits that can be reviewed well, and in reviewing commits by others
- Measurement: Query the Gerrit API

Number of unresolved Gerrit change requests authored by BioExcel developers is stable or decreasing compared with long-term baseline

- Justification: As above
- Measurement: Query the Gerrit API

7.2.5 Testing

All tests are in the source repository

- Justification: Tests not in the source repository are difficult to maintain and run in multiple build and runtime configurations
- Measurement: The number of tests remaining in the regressiontests repository used for testing master branch decreases

Test coverage is measured in an effective way

- Justification: Being able to assess whether code changes have test coverage is a valuable part of code review, and also influence decisions about effort to prioritise further testing. Coverage should be itemized by whether it is provided by unit, integration, or end-to-end tests.
- Measurement: A coverage build should run nightly (or perhaps per-commit) in CI

Test coverage is stable or increasing

- Justification: As above
- Measurement: Query the nightly coverage build

All Linux-based CI job types are done in containers

- Justification: It is wasteful to spend time of GROMACS developers on maintenance of multiple build agents with custom steups, and test coverage suffers because of the mis-spent resources. Users and developers will be better served with containerized infrastructure.
- Measurement: Count the remaining CI jobs run directly on Linux agents

Master-branch test matrices are up to date with recent releases of dependencies (e.g. compilers, libraries, OS)

- Justification: New versions of tools often provide new warnings that can help developers write better code.
- Measurement: A Redmine issue will be updated with a comment on which (if any) new major versions have been released

Number of TODO comments in CI matrices does not increase

- Justification: Changes should generally preserve the coverage and not require subsequent remedial action. TODO items should be gradually resolved. Adding TODO items is valuable only if someone plans to act upon them. If someone thinks a TODO item is valuable, that addition is much less valuable than either resolving it directly, or adding it while resolving a different TODO item.
- Measurement: Count the number of TODO comments in CI matrices

Issues found in post-submit, nightly and release CI testing matrices have been resolved in under a week.

- Justification: The current policy is that changes that introduce problems in configurations only tested after changes to master branch are submitted from Gerrit may be reverted if no fix is forthcoming within a week. This is intended to help prevent the build accumulating problems while waiting for developers to have time to fix problems.
- Measurement: A script observes whether the respective latest builds failed, and if so reports the duration since the last time the respective builds passed.

7.2.6 Release process

Patch releases of GROMACS occur no less than every three months

- Justification: Versions of the code with issues resolved need to be placed in the hands of the users in time to be useful during the period of active support for a branch.
- Measurement: Query the GROMACS download page for the date of the last release, but do not differentiate the branch of origin of the release, and ignore pre-release versions.

A release schedule for the coming year is announced in February each year

- Justification: Users are best served by a developer community that understands the expectations placed on them and can plan accordingly.
- Measurement: Observe that a post on gmx-developers mailing list has been made, and that a matching beta release target exists in Redmine.

A beta release of GROMACS takes place around mid-September each year

- Justification: Developers need a target to aim at for implementing new functionality, and a period of stabilizing the newly integrated functionality so that high-quality software can be released on time.
- Measurement: That the beta release is made within two weeks of the target date

A major release of GROMACS occurs around January 1 each year

- Justification: Users, developers, and their stakeholders wish to be able to rely on changed functionality becoming available in supported releases regularly and predictably.
- Measurement: That the first official release of a branch is made within two weeks of the target date

7.2.7 Meta KPIs

Automated KPI reporting for each proposed is in place

- Justification: Proposed KPIs that aren't reported are not useful, and if not automated as far as possible are less likely to show return on investment for measuring and making decisions
- Measurement: A Redmine wiki will collate the metrics and/or links to the place they are reported.

7.3 Software Capability

7.3.1 Co-design and future portability

Emerging architectures have been monitored and appropriate action planned.

- Justification: GROMACS is a widely used HPC application, and all stakeholders benefit if it can run (and preferably run well) on emerging architectures once they are in the hands of normal users (or will be very soon on procurement timelines)

- Measurement: A Redmine wiki page is updated quarterly with comments noting expected developments and the current status of plans, referring to Redmine issues where appropriate.

Vendor co-design projects are active

- Justification: Success in the extreme scale era will require collaboration between hardware vendors, software vendors/teams, and application teams, and this is expected of BioExcel.
- Measurement: A Redmine issue will be updated with a comment on which co-design projects are currently active

7.3.2 Performance and scalability

Performance benchmark set is designed and representative of multiple force fields (including AMBER, GROMOS, CHARMM, Martini families) and algorithms (including AWH, pulling, FEP)

- Justification: In order that developer effort be prioritised on projects that improve usability of the code, a representative set of performance benchmarks should exist. The data measured on this set will serve multiple purposes, including other KPIs below.
- Measurement: Such a benchmark set is available on the GROMACS website

GROMACS master branch performance on benchmark set (see above) improves

- Justification: Performance improvements and regressions should be observed, noted in release notes, or reconsidered. The related infrastructure will be useful for reporting to users the benefits of the newly released software.
- Measurement: Run a script on available representative modern hardware and record total performance of default mdrun on the simulations in the benchmark set. Where appropriate, re-run older code versions to establish baselines for comparison. Such scripts should target the following sub-cases important for current and near future usage profiles:
 - consumer-grade GPUs
 - professional-grade GPUs
 - single CPU-only node
 - single consumer-grade GPU per trajectory with few CPU cores
 - single consumer-grade GPU per trajectory with many CPU cores
 - scaling to multiple on-node GPUs per trajectory

GROMACS master branch performance on benchmark set (see above) offers nearly optimal performance without user guidance

- Justification: Improvements that only expert users can obtain delivers much lower impact. The related infrastructure will be useful for reporting to users the benefits of the newly released software.
- Measurement: Compare default mdrun performance with a parameter scan relevant to the hardware configuration and report the distribution of observed

performance. Such scripts should target the following sub-cases important for current and near future usage profiles:

- a single CPU-only node
- multiple CPU-only nodes
- a node with a single GPU
- a node with multiple GPUs
- Multiple nodes with GPU(s)

7.3.3 Feature support

GROMACS features needed for HADDOCK workflows are implemented

- Justification: A useful outcome for BioExcel will be that extreme scale workflows can be performed with fully free software using GROMACS as the back end. A set of required features has been identified and needs to be implemented.
- Measurement: That a set of related Redmine issues have been created and closed.

GROMACS supports Nudged Elastic Band method for characterizing transition states

- Justification: A useful outcome for BioExcel will be that QM/MM runs based around GROMACS can seek transition states using efficient methods well known to the user community.
- Measurement: That a set of related Redmine issues have been created and closed.

GROMACS has a new QM/MM interface

- Justification: A required outcome for BioExcel is that GROMACS can drive QM/MM simulations with QM back ends including CP2K.
- Measurement: That a set of related Redmine issues have been created and closed.

GROMACS supports additional force fields (if and only if they have a valid test set and enough active users to support any effort from BioExcel personnel)

- Justification: Users would like convenient access to widely used and trusted force fields, if they have been shown to work well with the simulation software.
- Measurement: That a set of related Redmine issues have been created and closed.

GROMACS can simulate guided by restraints derived from cryo-EM experiments

- Justification: A useful outcome for BioExcel would be to support functionality necessary for experimentally-guided simulations, and in particular for such guidance from cryo-EM simulations.
- Measurement: That a set of related Redmine issues have been created and closed.

GROMACS has a stable Python API

- Justification: Usability of GROMACS biomolecular simulations, preparation, analysis, and workflows will be greatly enhanced by a performant and flexible Python API. Less functionality will be required in the core simulation engine, and code not contributed to the core will be more likely to remain usable.

- Measurement: That a set of related Redmine issues have been created and closed.

GROMACS has a stable C++ API

- Justification: Usability of GROMACS biomolecular simulations, preparation, analysis, and workflows will be greatly enhanced by a performant C++ API. Less functionality will be required in the core simulation engine, and code not contributed to the core will be more likely to remain usable.
- Measurement: That a set of related Redmine issues have been created and closed.

GROMACS Python API permits trajectory analysis tasks without requiring preprocessing trajectory files

- Justification: Users have identified that guessing how to do pre-processing with trjconv is problematic, differs across gmx analysis tools, and requires time-consuming disk I/O. Instead tools should be able to declare their expectations, and the API runner applies transformations in memory as required.
- Measurement: That a set of related Redmine issues have been created and closed.

GROMACS Python API permits customized simulation preparation tasks

- Justification: Users have diverse simulation-preparation needs that cannot be supported with just a fixed set of C++ preparation tools.
- Measurement: That a set of related Redmine issues have been created and closed.

GROMACS implements lambda dynamics

- Justification: Such simulations cater to a potentially valuable niche of scientific questions, particularly for the pharma industry.
- Measurement: That a set of related Redmine issues have been created and closed.

Modules leveraging the GROMACS Python API for weakly coupled large ensembles are available

- Justification: Extreme scale biomolecular simulations will require such ensembles, and GROMACS should be known to be able to implement them well.
- Measurement: That a set of related Redmine issues have been created and closed.

GROMACS .tpr and .cpt formats have converged

- Justification: Long-standing usability and code maintenance issues will be resolved if there is only one file format that describes how to start a simulation from a configuration.
- Measurement: That a set of related Redmine issues have been created and closed.

GROMACS uses key-value serialized formats

- Justification: Much archaic file- and string-handling code can be retired with restructured input formats.
- Measurement: That a set of related Redmine issues have been created and closed, relating to the separate sub-projects pertaining to

- .mdp contents
- .tpr/.cpt contents
- .rtp/.atp contents
- .top/.itp contents

GROMACS defaults to TNG output

- Justification: Users and downstream projects will prefer the simplicity of a single container-style file to store and use.
- Measurement: That a set of related Redmine issues have been created and closed.

7.3.4 Deprecation

Number of deprecated features removed or replaced increases

- Justification: GROMACS is more usable if tools no longer thought to be widely used or useful are not available
- Measurement: Count the sections in the removed-functionality.rst files that contribute to the release notes and report the total over all such files

Number of deprecated features announced increases

- Justification: GROMACS users will do better science if functionality (or implementations of it) are known to be useful, and can plan downstream projects better with prior announcement of changes that will destabilize project workflows.
- Measurement: Count the sections in the deprecated-functionality.rst files that contribute to the release notes and report the total over all such files

7.3.5 User needs

A public software roadmap is available on the GROMACS website

- Justification: Users, vendors, developers and downstream projects would like to make plans based on reliable, up-to-date public information
- Measurement: That a named URL exists and comments on a Redmine issue reflect that updates are required, or not.

Total citation rate of core GROMACS papers does not decrease

- Justification: If the citation rate would start to decrease, this might indicate the presence of alternative software or algorithms affecting the market share. If so, the development team should seek external input and development strategy should be reconsidered.
- Measurement: That a script calls an external API (e.g. Google Scholar) to record citation counts of “official” GROMACS papers.